

Bilastine with Montelukast and Fexofenadine with Montelukast in Allergic Rhinitis: A Randomized Control TrialSwati Prasad¹, Shradha Chandra², Helena Babu³¹Post Graduate Student, Department of ENT, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India²Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India³Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Allergic rhinitis is a global disease. It is an inflammatory disease affecting the mucosa of nasal cavity caused by exposure to an allergen which triggers IgE-mediated inflammation. There are four major symptoms of Allergic Rhinitis which includes –sneezing, rhinorrhea, nasal itching, and nasal congestion. The mainstay of management of allergic rhinitis is avoidance of allergens. Other treatments include intranasal corticosteroids, short term nasal decongestants, oral or topical H1 receptor antagonists (antihistamines), anticholinergic agents, intranasal cromoglycate, and allergen immunotherapy.

Materials and Methodology: The present study has been performed to compare the efficacy of fexofenadine with montelukast versus Bilastine with montelukast in the patients with Allergic Rhinitis of either gender between the age of 18–60 years at a tertiary care teaching institution from November 1, 2022, to October 31, 2023.

Observation and Results: In our investigation, we found the disease to be more common in younger 21-30 age group and middle-income category. In total nasal symptom score, sneezing has the highest score of 2.25 ± 0.5 , followed by runny nose with 2.0 ± 0.8 and difficulty in sleeping had the least score of 1.2 ± 0.8

Conclusion: Allergic rhinitis is one of the most common immunologic and chronic disease experienced by humans. In our investigation, we found the disease to be more common in younger 21-30 age group and middle-income category. Majority of the subjects suffered from seasonal allergic rhinitis. Oral Bilastine with Montelukast were significantly superior when compared to Oral Fexofenadine with Montelukast. Bilastine with Montelukast was found to be more efficacious and provided more symptoms free duration.

Keywords: Allergic Rhinitis, Bilastine, Montelukast, Fexofenadine.

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Introduction

Allergic rhinitis is a global disease. It is an inflammatory disease affecting the mucosa of nasal cavity caused by exposure to an allergen which triggers IgE-mediated inflammation. There are four major symptoms of Allergic Rhinitis which includes – sneezing, rhinorrhea, nasal itching, and nasal congestion. It can also be associated with Asthma, Atopic Dermatitis & Nasal polyps. In India, around 20-30% suffer from allergic rhinitis. Quality of life, routine work, sleep, and school performance has been seen reduced by the clinical symptoms of allergic rhinitis.

Allergic rhinitis was earlier subdivided, based on time of exposure, into seasonal, occupational, and perennial. This subdivision was not completely satisfactory. The basis of guidelines for recent classification of Allergic rhinitis as proposed by ARIA

(Allergic Rhinitis and its Impact on Asthma) is: Duration as “intermittent” or “persistent” disease, Severity of symptoms and quality of life as “mild” or “moderate-severe” [1]

The TH2 cells pledge the type 1 hypersensitivity reaction seen in allergic rhinitis and characterized by pollen-induced rhinitis. During sensitization phase, the immune system classifies the foreign allergen and makes specific IgE antibodies in response. Allergic Rhinitis can be managed by avoidance of allergen and medications that give symptomatic relief. Oral antihistamines are one of the mostly used medications for treatment of Allergic rhinitis [2]. Newer non-sedating antihistamines were established to be less soluble, limiting their capability to enter the Blood brain barrier [3]. The mainstay of management of allergic rhinitis is

avoidance of allergens. Other treatments include intranasal corticosteroids, short term nasal decongestants, oral or topical H1 receptor antagonists (antihistamines), anticholinergic agents, intranasal cromoglycate, and allergen immunotherapy.

Materials & Methods

The open label randomized control trial study has been performed to compare the efficacy of fexofenadine with montelukast versus Bilastine with montelukast in the patients with Allergic Rhinitis of either gender between the ages of 18–60 years at a tertiary care teaching institution in western Uttar Pradesh for a period of 1 year from November 1, 2022, to October 31, 2023. An ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee before starting the study.

Sample Size: Total = 182 cases.

Group A: This group included 91 patients on Fexofenadine with Montelukast. Group B: This group included 91 patients on Bilastine with Montelukast.

Inclusion Criteria

- All patients willing to participate in this study.
- All patients including both the gender above the age of 18 years.
- All cases having symptom of Allergic Rhinitis.

Exclusion Criteria

- Female patients during Pregnancy and Lactation.
- Patients with Hypertensive Heart Disease, Diabetes mellitus, Thyroid Dysfunction.
- Patients with nasal mass.
- Patients with past history of nasal surgery.

The candidates having symptoms of Allergic Rhinitis were randomly divided into Group A (Fexofenadine with Montelukast) and Group B (Bilastine with Montelukast). Patients with odd serial no. were added to group A and patients with even serial no. were added to group B.

- In group A, Fexofenadine with Montelukast was given for 4 weeks and will be followed up further 4 weeks (0, 2 and 4 weeks)
- In group B, Bilastine with Montelukast was given for 4 weeks and will be followed up further 4 weeks (0, 2 and 4 weeks)

To conclude the prevalence of allergic rhinitis in our study population, the score for allergic rhinitis (SFAR) was used. The SFAR include eight components, which are as follows:

1. Nasal symptoms in last one year, including runny nose, sneezing, and blocked nose
2. Nasal symptoms supplemented with itchy-watery eyes (rhinoconjunctivitis)

3. Month in which the nasal symptoms appeared
4. Triggers for the nasal symptoms, including pollens, danders and house dust
5. Apparent allergic status
6. Preceding medical diagnosis of allergy
7. Preceding positive allergen test; and
8. Familial history of allergy if any

The total nasal symptom score (TNSS) was used to assess the allergic rhinitis. The TNSS involves five components, including the following:

1. Please rate how your nasal congestion has been over the past: Mild, moderate, and severe
2. Please rate how your runny nose has been over the past: Mild, moderate, and severe
3. Please rate how your nasal itching has been over the past: Mild, moderate, and severe
4. Please rate how your sneezing has been over the past: Mild, moderate, and severe
5. Please rate how difficult sleep has been with nasal symptoms: Mild, moderate, and severe

Observation and Results

Age Group Distribution: In our study, age of patients was in range from 18 to 60 years. The youngest was 18 years and the eldest was 60 years. In both group A & B, maximum number of cases were in between 21-30 years age group.

Gender Distribution: In Our study out of 91 cases in Group A, 62.64% were male and 37.36% were female and out of 91 cases in Group B, 58.24% were male and 41.76% were female. There was no significant difference in gender of patients in between Group A and Group B.

Income Distribution: Out of 91 cases, majority 58(63.7%) patients belonged to low-income category followed by Middle income category 29 cases (31.9%) and with only 4 cases (4.4%) in high income category in Group A and similar findings was seen in group B with 56(61.5%), 29(31.9%), 6(6.6%) patients belong to low, middle, high income category respectively. However, no significant difference in Income of patients in between Group A and Group B.

Duration of Presentation: Out of 91 cases in Group A, Maximum 51.6% of individuals with allergic rhinitis were presenting their symptoms duration was of 6 month to 1 years followed by 34.1 % of < 6 months and 14.3% in cases of > 1 year whereas in Group B out of 91 cases Maximum 53.8% of individuals with allergic rhinitis were presenting their symptoms duration was 6 month to 1 year followed by 34.1 % of <6 months and 12.1% in cases of > 1 year and in Group B. There was no significant difference in with allergic rhinitis were presenting their symptoms duration of patients in between Group A and Group B.

Seasonal Versus Perennial: Both the group A and

B showed maximum cases as seasonal allergic rhinitis presentation with 68(74.73%) and 69(75.82%) cases in Group A and Group B respectively. There were 23(25.27%) in group A and 22(24.18%) cases in group B with perennial allergic rhinitis. There was no significant difference in presenting their symptoms in seasonal and perennial in patients in between Group A and Group B.

Season Wise Distribution: Out of 91 cases in Group A, Maximum 36(39.6%) of patients of seasonal allergic rhinitis presented during winter and Monsoon season followed by with 19(20.9%) cases in summer season, In Group B Maximum 36(39.6%) cases presented with seasonal allergic rhinitis in winter season followed by Monsoon season 32(35.2%) cases and summer in 23(25.3%) cases.

Therefore, there was no significant difference found in respect to seasonal variation in the two groups.

Family History

- A. A total of 44 (24.2%) patients had positive family history. Total SFAR Mean Total SFAR was 5.16 ± 1.23 in patients of Group A and 5.03 ± 1.15 in patients of Group B.
- B. There was no significant difference in Mean Total SFAR of patients in between Group A and Group B.

TNSS: In total nasal symptom score, sneezing has the highest score of 2.25 ± 0.5 , followed by runny nose with 2.0 ± 0.8 and difficulty in sleeping had the least score of 1.2 ± 0.8 .

Table 1: Age group

Age Group(in years)	Group A		Group B		P-Value
	Number	%	Number	%	
≤20	11	12.09	9	9.89	0.054
21-30	32	35.16	33	36.26	
31-40	17	18.68	25	27.47	
41-50	17	18.68	18	19.78	
51-60	14	15.38	6	6.59	
Total	91	100.00	91	100.00	
Mean age	35.13 ± 13.1		33.99 ± 10.82		
Range	18-60		18-60		

Figure 1: Age group (In Years)

Table 2: Sex Distribution

Sex	Group A		Group B		P-Value
	Number	%	Number	%	
Male	57	62.64	53	58.24	0.544
Female	24	37.36	38	41.76	
Total	91	100.0	91	100.0	

Figure 2: Gender

Table 3: Income Distribution

Income(In Rs)	Group A		Group B		P-Value
	Number	%	Number	%	
<20000	58	63.7	56	61.5	0.840
20000-60000	29	31.9	29	31.9	
>60000	4	4.4	6	6.6	
Total	91	100	91	100	

Figure 3: Income (In Rs.)

Table 4: Duration of presentation

Duration	Group A		Group B		P-Value
	Number	%	Number	%	
<6 Months	31	34.1	31	34.1	0.901
6month-1year	47	51.6	49	53.8	
>1year	13	14.3	11	12.1	
Total	91	100.0	91	100.0	

Figure 4: Duration of presentation

Table 5: Seasonal versus perennial

Season	Group A		Group B		P-Value
	Number	%	Number	%	
Seasonal	68	74.73	69	75.82	0.862
Perennial	23	25.27	22	24.18	
Total	91	100.0	91	100.0	

Figure 5: Seasonal V/S Perennial

Table 6: Season wise distribution

Season	Group A		Group B		P-Value
	Number	%	Number	%	
Summer	19	20.9	23	25.3	0.735
Winter	36	39.6	36	39.6	
Monsoon	36	39.6	32	35.2	
Total	91	100.0	91	100.0	

Figure 6: Seasonal Variation

Table 7: Comparison of Mean total score for allergic rhinitis

	Group A	Group B	P-Value
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	
Baseline	10.19 ± 2.2	10.12 ± 2.25	0.842
2nd visit	6.3 ± 2.2	5.4 ± 2.3	0.719
3rd visit	3.2 ± 2.0	2.7 ± 2.1	0.126

Figure 7: Mean TNSS

Table 8: Comparison of % of reduction of TNSS in Group A and Group B

	Group A	Group B	
Visit	Percentage of Reduction	Percentage of Reduction	Difference
2nd visit	38.2%	46.6%	8.5%
3rd visit	68.6%	73.3%	4.7%

Figure 8: % of reduction of total TNSS

Discussion

The age of patients was in the range from 18 to 60 years. The youngest was 18 years and the eldest was 60 years. Maximum number of cases in Group A were in between 21-30 years (35.16%) with mean age of 35.13 ± 13.1 years. In Group B maximum number of cases were in between 21-30 years (36.26%) having an average age of 33.99 ± 10.82 years.

Our findings is in line with the study done by Meltzer EO et al.[1], Adelsberget al. (2002) [2], Mahatme MS et al. (2016) [3], Yildiz E et al. (2019) [4] and Achankunju S Aet al. (2021)[5].The possible reason as to why this age group is most effected is the activity and lifestyle which increases the chances of bringing them into contact with a wide variety of allergens as compared to the older age group.

Out of 91 cases in Group A, 62.64% were male and 37.36% were female and out of 91 cases in Group B, 58.24% were male and 41.76% were female. Similar results found in study conducted by Mishra et al.[6] with male (39.7%) and female (60.3%),Yildiz E et al. (2019) [4] with male (50%) and female (50%). Allergic rhinitis does not differ in its presentation and clinical course between males and females. Hence this difference in sex does not affect the comparison of groups, who were selected after randomization.

majority (63.7%) of subjects belonged to Low-income category followed by Middle income category (31.9%) and by High in 4.4% in Group A

and study majority (61.5%) of subjects belonged to Low income category followed by Middle income category (31.9%) and by High in 6.6% in Group B which reflects on the income group of the population attending our out-patient's department. Our findings were found to be in line with the study done Mösge Ret al. (2015) [7]. In our study maximum Patients with allergic rhinitis were presenting their symptoms duration was 6 months to 1 year followed by <6 months and then > 1 year. Also, maximum patients were symptomatic during Winter and Monsoon season followed by summer in both group A and b. Hence proving that the maximum no of patients were found to be symptomatic during winter and monsoon season with duration of 6months to 1 year. Our findings were found to be in line with the study done by Nayak A and Langdon et al.[8] and Kaur G et al. (2016)[9] with 40.3% and 39.4% in winter and monsoon season respectively. A total of 44 (24.2%) patients had positive family history.

In the present study to assess the efficacy of two drugs Oral Fexofenadine with Montelukast and Oral Bilastine with Montelukast in 182 subjects diagnosed to have allergic rhinitis were treated with one of the two combinations of drugs after randomization for eight weeks. For the diagnosis of allergic rhinitis SFAR score was used and, in our study mean Total SFAR was 5.16 ± 1.23 in patients of Group A and 5.03 ± 1.15 in patients of Group B. There was no notable distinction in Mean Total SFAR of patients in between Group A and Group B. Comparable findings were observed in study

done by Randhawa AS et al.(2022)¹⁰where mean total was determined to be 5.7 ± 1.35 in the patients of allergic rhinitis and was found to be effective in diagnosing the disease.

Conclusion

Allergic rhinitis is one of the most common immunologic and chronic disease experienced by humans. In our investigation, we found the disease to be more common in younger 21-30 age group and middle-income category. Majority of the subjects suffered from seasonal allergic rhinitis. Oral Bilastine with Montelukast were significantly superior when compared to Oral Fexofenadine with Montelukast. Bilastine with Montelukast was found to be more efficacious and provided more symptoms free duration.

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